

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHER-CENTERED APPROACH IN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

Islomova Dilnoza

student of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Khudoykulova Madina

student of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Yugay Evgeniya Viktorovna

a scientific adviser, a senior teacher of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract: Teacher-centered instruction focuses mainly on the educator. All the classroom activities are mostly relied on the teacher’s plan, design and directions. Students in that case are totally under the control, which notably reduces the possibility of the learners missing any essential content. Compared with student-centered classroom, students in teacher-centered classroom are passive and respond to environmental stimuli. Teacher has the ultimate authority and is in charge of learning for that reason students do not have opportunities to develop their critical thinking and problem-solving skills. This article endeavors to discuss to what extent the teacher-centered approach is essential in recent educational system.

Key words: teacher-centered approach, student-centered approach, classroom instructions, stimuli.

Introduction

Educators always had to search for the ideal method to implement in the classroom for effective learning and teaching. Nevertheless, classrooms operate either with teacher-centered or student-centered approaches. The use of traditional methods has received criticism for not creating an environment in the classroom to develop critical thinking and problem solving skills. For that reason, there has been a shift from teacher-centered to student-centered approach in classroom instruction.

The approach based on the teacher refers educate students in a learning environment in which the teacher has the primary responsibility (Mascolo, 2009). Lectures are solely used as a means of dissemination of knowledge to students. While teachers are active, students are passive in teacher-centered classroom. In contrast to teacher-centered, student-centered instruction provides a learning setting to the students in which they construct their skills and understanding. However, in teacher-centered classroom, there is a false assumption that teachers have a diminishing role in the learning process. Rather, teachers have facilitating role and it is not eliminated in the learning process. Similarly, in student-centered classroom students are not able make their mind by themselves instead teachers help to improve their critical

thinking.

Literature Review

Teacher-centered approach relied on the theory which was based on the idea that behavior changes are caused by external stimuli (Skinner, 1974). According to the theory students are passive and respond to environmental stimuli. In teacher-centered classrooms, the teacher is in charge of learning; therefore, he/she transmits knowledge to the students. As the teacher holds the ultimate authority, the students do not collaborate. The content is decided and the learning tasks are structured by the teacher. The instruction is delivered through lecturing and provision of feedback and correct answers are widely used. The teacher is the primary source of information and the textbook is the center of activities. Peyton, More and Young (2010) stated that:

In a typical teacher-centered classroom, the teacher spends most of the time presenting the day's content to the class from the whiteboard or overhead projector.

The students should be taking notes and asking questions during the lecture. This process should be completed with ease and not troublesome for students (p.21).

Control has been priority in teacher-centered classrooms for that reason; teacher-based way in learning system has received criticism for favoring passive students rather than active ones in the classroom (Freiberg, 1999). However, it should be stated that being under the push, students are rather focused and tend to show interest in the subject. For that reason, some researchers support the use of teacher-centered approach because it allows teaching learners in short steps (Espenshade & Radford, 2009).

Method

Participants

The experiment included 100 undergraduate-student volunteers, 50 of them are boys and the others are girls. Students were divided into two groups. The former worked with a teacher and the latest on their own based on student-based approach. All of the participants were potential learners. Those who were struggling with their studies were excluded, as they might give fake information because of their low comprehension.

Materials

An online teaching channel was created in Telegram platform. The testing subject was ‘English language as a target language’. Each volunteer was invited to the channel as there was given the syllabus of the subject. The experiment continued a month.

Procedure

Pupils from group1 were supposed to be prepared with their tasks based on curriculum on their own on a daily basis. Every Monday, Thursday and Saturday lessons were held in a student-centered approach. Therefore, pupils worked

individually according to the program. On the other hand, students from group 2 were captured by a teacher.

The themes the experiment covered:

- Theme1. Now and then;
- Theme2. The environment;
- Theme3. Space.

Results

By the end of the month, the research revealed that volunteers from ‘student-centered’ group were more irresponsible, absent-minded and uninitiated. That was due to the fact that students were teenagers. And teenagers, in turn, need constant supervision, care and support. In contrast, learners who worked with a teacher were rather disciplined and motivated.

The observation found out that those who were taught, directed and motivated by the teacher came over with higher results rather than volunteers on their own. Group 1(Student-centered group) was very absent, irresponsible and idle. Contrariwise, the second group (Teacher-based) prospered at the final exam we took. To compare, group1 achieve 67% and group2 scored 98% from 100% scaled tests respectively.

Discussion

The aim of the research was to prove the significance of learning language with a teacher. The teacher-based way of educating has been widely criticized because of the absolute control of the students that is in priority. It should be noted that the primary goal in the classroom is to empower learning. In this respect, teachers in

order to maintain control over students need to ensure that they enable the students to participate actively in the classroom activities. If teachers are well-informed in the content they present and might apply motivational strategies while teaching, students keep their attention, are actively engaged in activities and become academically successful.

Furthermore, building a comfortable learning environment is an essential factor in student achievement. With this in regard, student-centered classroom pervades activities which create fun. Also, the impact of self-confidence in achievement cannot be underestimated. That students take an active role, easily present information to the others and share classroom responsibilities, increase their self-confidence.

Conclusion

The article tried to discuss and support the importance of teacher-centered approach in our times. Despite the fact that student-centered approach provides learners much more freedom in their behavior and studies, the teacher-based one is considered to be the most effective in educational system. That is due to the educator's informative design, plan of the lesson. In comparison, 'freelancers' in education are likely to respond to external stimuli. On the other hand, students having been under the teacher's supervision show greater enthusiasm during the lessons and classroom activities. Therefore, they tend to be the most prosperous students as they are better disciplined.

To summarize, teacher-centered approach is still relevant today and has thousands of fans who will continue to maintain it.

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